

Properties and Structure of Type-2 Neutrosophic Control Point Relation

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Abstract: In recent decades, practitioners and scholars from several fields have increasingly used fuzzy sets as a fundamental tool for characterizing uncertainty data. Uncertainty or indeterminacy data cannot be directly modeled since gathering reliable information for analysis or prediction is difficult. Hence, this study contributes to another theory by visualizing the type-2 neutrosophic set (T2NS) in geometric modeling onto indeterminacy data established using the type-2 fuzzy ideas. T2NS represents the generalized forms of fuzzy sets, intuitionistic fuzzy sets, neutrosophic sets, interval-valued fuzzy sets, interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy sets, and interval-valued neutrosophic sets. Thus, the type-2 neutrosophic control point relation (T2NCPR) will be presented with some numerical examples. Additionally, the properties and structures of T2NCPR will be discussed. Finally, the proposed approaches are reliable and may be applied to a wide range of applications.

Keywords: Type-2 Neutrosophic Set Theory; Type-2 Neutrosophic Control Point Relation; The Properties and Structures.

1. Introduction

To deal with uncertainties, many theories have been created, including probability theory, intuitionistic fuzzy set theory, fuzzy set theory, rough set theory, and many more. Smarandache [1,2] initially proposed the neutrosophic set (NS) idea in 1999. It involves an independent indeterminacy membership. This function generalizes a few novel set theories, including fuzzy sets [3], intuitionistic fuzzy sets [4], and classic sets. To determine truth-membership (T), indeterminacy-membership (I), and false-membership (F) in a neutrosophic set (NS), the three distinct functions are employed. These degrees function independently from one another.

Based on Mendel and John [4], type-1 fuzzy sets cannot directly model uncertainties due to their crisp membership functions. However, type-2 fuzzy sets (T2FS) can handle uncertainties as their membership functions are also fuzzy. Additionally, type-1 fuzzy sets have two-dimensional membership functions, while type-2 fuzzy sets have three-dimensional functions. There are some researchers were employed T2FS in their studies [5-10]. Basset et al. [11] were the first authors to introduce the fundamental notion of type-2 neutrosophic number (T2NN) while Bakali and Broumi [12] illustrated the graphical representation of type-2 neutrosophic set (T2NS). Additionally, other studies used T2NS in their application [13-16].

Neutrosophic sets can address curve and surface construction issues in computer-aided graphic designs (CAGD). This notion is essential to create a smoother curve or surface model. NS and CAGD are two strategies for resolving ambiguity in control or data points. Wahab [17-19] developed a method for fuzzifying control points to generate Bézier and B-spline curves. The study of fuzzy set theory and geometric modeling has grown in [20-25]. Aside from that, some works blended the neutrosophic set theory with geometric modeling [26-35, 39-42]. Nonetheless, no study has been conducted on displaying structures and properties of type-2 neutrosophic control point relation which is the important part of generating any neutrosophic geometric modeling.

The following is an overview of the work. The first part provides background information on the topic. Section 2 discusses several T2NS theories and some related definitions. Section 3 will introduce the type-2 neutrosophic control point relation (T2NCPR). Some numerical examples will be presented in this section. Section 4 shows and describes the properties and structures of T2NCPR. Section 5 ends with a discussion and conclusions.

2. Preliminaries

This section will discuss some of the basic definitions based on previous studies. The definitions are the fundamental notions of T2FS, NS, T2NS, and some properties and structures of NS that will be used in the next sections. Therefore, the definitions are as follows:

Definition 1. [5] A type-2 fuzzy set, denoted \tilde{A} is characterized by a secondary membership function $\mu_{\tilde{A}}(x, u)$ where $x \in X$ and u as primary membership in $J_x \subseteq [0, 1]$. i. e.,

$$\tilde{A} = \{((x, u), \mu_{\tilde{A}}(x, u)) \mid \forall x \in X, \forall u \in J_x \subseteq [0, 1]\} \tag{1}$$

In which $0 \leq \mu_{\tilde{A}}(x, u) \leq 1$. \tilde{A} can also be expressed as

$$\tilde{A} = \int_{x \in X} \int_{u \in J_x} \frac{\mu_{\tilde{A}}(x, u)}{(x, u)} \quad J_x \subseteq [0, 1] \tag{2}$$

where \int denotes union over all admissible x and u . For discrete universes of discourse \int is replaced by \sum .

Definition 2. [1] Let X be the universal set, with elements in X represented as x . The neutrosophic set is an element in the structure as follows:

$$\hat{A} = \{ \langle x : T_{\hat{A}(x)}, I_{\hat{A}(x)}, F_{\hat{A}(x)} \rangle \mid x \in X \} \tag{3}$$

where $T, I, F : X \rightarrow]0, 1+[$ represented as the degree of truth, indeterminacy, and falsity memberships respectively of the element $x \in X$ to the set \hat{A} with the condition;

$$0^- \leq T_{\hat{A}}(x) + I_{\hat{A}}(x) + F_{\hat{A}}(x) \leq 3^+ \tag{4}$$

There is no limit to the amount of $T_{\hat{A}}(x), I_{\hat{A}}(x)$ and $F_{\hat{A}}(x)$.

NS takes the value from real standard or non-standard subsets of $]0, 1+[$. But in technical applications the real value of the interval $[0, 1]$ will be used since $]0, 1+[$ difficult to apply in real data such as scientific and engineering problems. Thus, the membership values used as follows:

$$\hat{A} = \{ \langle x : T_{\hat{A}(x)}, I_{\hat{A}(x)}, F_{\hat{A}(x)} \rangle \mid x \in X \} \text{ and } T_{\hat{A}}(x), I_{\hat{A}}(x), F_{\hat{A}}(x) \in [0, 1]$$

There is no limitation on the summation of $T_{\hat{A}}(x), I_{\hat{A}}(x)$ and $F_{\hat{A}}(x)$. But comply with the following conditions:

$$0 \leq T_{\hat{A}}(x) + I_{\hat{A}}(x) + F_{\hat{A}}(x) \leq 3 \tag{5}$$

Definition 3. [36]

Let \hat{A} is a neutrosophic number in real numbers, \square and its properties are as follows:

1. \hat{A} is normal, ie., if exist $x_0 \in \square$ such that $T_{\hat{A}}(x_0) = 1$ while $I_{\hat{A}}(x_0) = F_{\hat{A}}(x_0) = 0$.
2. \hat{A} is convex set for truth function $T_{\hat{A}}(x)$, that is, $T_{\hat{A}}(\mu x_1 + (1 - \mu)x_2) \geq \min(T_{\hat{A}}(x_1), T_{\hat{A}}(x_2)), \forall x_1, x_2 \in \square, \mu \in [0, 1]$.
3. \hat{A} is concave set for indeterminacy $I_{\hat{A}}(x)$ and false function $F_{\hat{A}}(x)$, that is, $I_{\hat{A}}(\mu x_1 + (1 - \mu)x_2) \geq \max(I_{\hat{A}}(x_1), I_{\hat{A}}(x_2)), \forall x_1, x_2 \in \square, \mu \in [0, 1]$ and $F_{\hat{A}}(\mu x_1 + (1 - \mu)x_2) \geq \max(F_{\hat{A}}(x_1), F_{\hat{A}}(x_2)), \forall x_1, x_2 \in \square, \mu \in [0, 1]$.

Definition 4. [26,27]

Let $\hat{A} = \{x : T_{\hat{A}}(x), I_{\hat{A}}(x), F_{\hat{A}}(x) \mid x \in \hat{A}\}$ and $\hat{B} = \{y : T_{\hat{B}}(y), I_{\hat{B}}(y), F_{\hat{B}}(y) \mid y \in \hat{B}\}$ be neutrosophic elements. Thus, $NR = \{(x, y) : T(x, y), I(x, y), F(x, y) \mid x \in \hat{A}, y \in \hat{B}\}$ is a neutrosophic relation on \hat{A} and \hat{B} .

Definition 5. [37]

Let X and Y be two NSs over the universal sets U and V , respectively. The Cartesian product of X and Y denoted by $X \times Y$ is an NS defined as $X \times Y = \{(u, v), T_{X \times Y}(u, v), I_{X \times Y}(u, v), F_{X \times Y}(u, v) : (u, v) \in U \times V\}$, where $T_{X \times Y}(u, v)$ is truth membership function, $I_{X \times Y}(u, v)$ is indeterminacy membership function and $F_{X \times Y}(u, v)$ is falsity membership function and $\forall (u, v) \in U \times V$,

$$\begin{aligned} T_{X \times Y}(u, v) &= \min(X(u), Y(v)) \\ I_{X \times Y}(u, v) &= \max(X(u), Y(v)) \\ F_{X \times Y}(u, v) &= \max(X(u), Y(v)) \end{aligned}$$

Definition 6. [38]

Let $x \in X$ where X is a neutrosophic set and $x_{\alpha, \beta, \gamma} \in X$. Then,

1. $x_{\alpha, \beta, \gamma}$ is said to be contained in \hat{A} , denoted by $x_{\alpha, \beta, \gamma} \subseteq \hat{A}$, if and only if $\alpha \leq T_{\hat{A}}(x)$, $\beta \geq I_{\hat{A}}(x)$ and $\gamma \geq F_{\hat{A}}(x)$.
2. $x_{\alpha, \beta, \gamma}$ is said to belong to \hat{A} , denoted by $x_{\alpha, \beta, \gamma} \in \hat{A}$, if and only if $\alpha \leq T_{\hat{A}}(x)$, $\beta \geq I_{\hat{A}}(x)$ and $\gamma \geq F_{\hat{A}}(x)$.
3. A neutrosophic control point $x_{1,0,0} \subseteq \hat{A}$ if and only if $T_{\hat{A}}(x) = 1, I_{\hat{A}}(x) = 0$, and $F_{\hat{A}}(x) = 0$.
4. A neutrosophic control point $x_{1,0,0} \in \hat{A}$ if and only if $T_{\hat{A}}(x) = 1, I_{\hat{A}}(x) = 0$, and $F_{\hat{A}}(x) = 0$.

Proposition 1 [38]

Every NS \hat{A} can be expressed as the union of all neutrosophic points (NP) contained in \hat{A} .

Proof: Let $\hat{B} = \cup \{x_{\alpha, \beta, \gamma} : x_{\alpha, \beta, \gamma} \in \hat{A}\}$, where $x \in X$. If $T_{\hat{A}} \neq 0, I_{\hat{A}} \neq 1, F_{\hat{A}} \neq 1$ then,

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{\hat{A}}(x) &= \sup \{ \alpha : x_{\alpha, \beta, \gamma} \text{ is a NP and } \alpha \leq T_{\hat{A}}(x), \beta \geq I_{\hat{A}}(x), \gamma \geq F_{\hat{A}}(x) \} \\
 &= T_{\cup x_{\alpha, \beta, \gamma}}(x) \\
 &= T_{\hat{B}(x)} \\
 I_{\hat{A}}(x) &= \inf \{ \beta : x_{\alpha, \beta, \gamma} \text{ is a NP and } \alpha \leq T_{\hat{A}}(x), \beta \geq I_{\hat{A}}(x), \gamma \geq F_{\hat{A}}(x) \} \\
 &= I_{\cup x_{\alpha, \beta, \gamma}}(x) \\
 &= I_{\hat{B}(x)} \\
 F_{\hat{A}}(x) &= \inf \{ \gamma : x_{\alpha, \beta, \gamma} \text{ is a NP and } \alpha \leq T_{\hat{A}}(x), \beta \geq I_{\hat{A}}(x), \gamma \geq F_{\hat{A}}(x) \} \\
 &= F_{\cup x_{\alpha, \beta, \gamma}}(x) \\
 &= F_{\hat{B}(x)}
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\hat{A} = \hat{B}$, that is, $\hat{A} = \cup \{ x_{\alpha, \beta, \gamma} : x_{\alpha, \beta, \gamma} \in A \}$.

Definition 7 [13] A type-2 neutrosophic set, denoted \hat{A} is characterized by a secondary truth membership function $\mu_{\hat{A}}(x, T)$, secondary indeterminacy membership function $\eta_{\hat{A}}(x, I)$ and secondary falsity membership function $\nu_{\hat{A}}(x, F)$ where $x \in X$ and T, I, F as primary truth membership function, primary indeterminacy membership function, and primary falsity membership function respectively in $J_x^T, J_x^I, J_x^F \subseteq [0, 1]$. i. e.,

$$\hat{A} = \left\{ \left((x, T, I, F), (\mu_{\hat{A}}(x, T), \eta_{\hat{A}}(x, I), \nu_{\hat{A}}(x, F)) \right) \mid \forall x \in X, \mu_{\hat{A}} \in J_x^T, \eta_{\hat{A}} \in J_x^I, \nu_{\hat{A}} \in J_x^F \right\} \tag{6}$$

In which $0 \leq \mu_{\hat{A}}(x, T) \leq 1$, $0 \leq \eta_{\hat{A}}(x, I) \leq 1$ and $0 \leq \nu_{\hat{A}}(x, F) \leq 1$. \hat{A} can also be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \hat{A}_T &= \int_{x \in X} \int_{T \in J_x^T} \frac{\mu_{\hat{A}}(x, T)}{(x, T)} & J_x^T &\subseteq [0, 1] \\
 \hat{A}_I &= \int_{x \in X} \int_{I \in J_x^I} \frac{\eta_{\hat{A}}(x, I)}{(x, I)} & J_x^I &\subseteq [0, 1] \\
 \hat{A}_F &= \int_{x \in X} \int_{F \in J_x^F} \frac{\nu_{\hat{A}}(x, F)}{(x, F)} & J_x^F &\subseteq [0, 1]
 \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

3. Type-2 Neutrosophic Control Point Relation (T2NCPR)

Control points are a vital element in creating curves and surfaces and are crucial for data analysis. They are used to define and regulate the behavior of curves or surfaces. To accomplish the section's goal, the T2NCPR is established based on the concept and theory of T2NS. In this section, T2NCPR and some of its concepts are introduced through the type-2 neutrosophic point relation (T2NPR), which is used to represent data with neutrosophic characteristics in this study.

Definition 8 (Type-2 Neutrosophic Point Relation)

Let X and Y is the collection of point sets, thus \hat{R} , is T2NPR defined as

$$\hat{R} = \left\{ \left\langle \left((x_i, y_j), T_R(x_i, y_j), I_R(x_i, y_j), F_R(x_i, y_j), \mu_R(x_i, y_j), \eta_R(x_i, y_j), \nu_R(x_i, y_j)) \right) \right\rangle \right\} \quad (8)$$

$$\left\{ \left. \left. T_R(x_i, y_j), I_R(x_i, y_j), F_R(x_i, y_j), \mu_R(x_i, y_j), \eta_R(x_i, y_j), \nu_R(x_i, y_j) \in S \right. \right\}$$

where $S \in [0,1]$, $T_R(x_i, y_j): X \times Y \rightarrow S$, $I_R(x_i, y_j): X \times Y \rightarrow S$, $F_R(x_i, y_j): X \times Y \rightarrow S$, $\mu_R(x_i, y_j): X \times Y \rightarrow S$, $\eta_R(x_i, y_j): X \times Y \rightarrow S$ and $\nu_R(x_i, y_j): X \times Y \rightarrow S$ that obey the condition

$$0 \leq T_R(x_i, y_j) + I_R(x_i, y_j) + F_R(x_i, y_j) \leq 3 \quad (9)$$

where $T_R(x_i, y_j), I_R(x_i, y_j), F_R(x_i, y_j), \mu_R(x_i, y_j), \eta_R(x_i, y_j), \nu_R(x_i, y_j) \rightarrow [0,1]$ for all $(x_i, y_j) \in X \times Y$.

From Equations (4.1), \hat{R} are represented as T2NPR that consists of neutrosophic relation point denoted as R^T , R^I , R^F , R^μ , R^η and R^ν for truth, indeterminacy, and falsity for primary and secondary memberships, respectively. If Equations (4.2) is fulfilled, there exists R^T , R^I , R^F , R^μ , R^η and R^ν that is stated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} R^T &= \left\{ \left\langle (x_i, y_j), T_R(x_i, y_j) \right\rangle \mid T_R(x_i, y_j) \in S \right\}; \\ R^\mu &= \left\{ \left\langle (x_i, y_j), \mu_R(x_i, y_j) \right\rangle \mid \mu_R(x_i, y_j) \in S \right\}; \\ R^I &= \left\{ \left\langle (x_i, y_j), I_R(x_i, y_j) \right\rangle \mid I_R(x_i, y_j) \in S \right\}; \\ R^\eta &= \left\{ \left\langle (x_i, y_j), \eta_R(x_i, y_j) \right\rangle \mid \eta_R(x_i, y_j) \in S \right\}; \\ R^F &= \left\{ \left\langle (x_i, y_j), F_R(x_i, y_j) \right\rangle \mid F_R(x_i, y_j) \in S \right\}; \\ R^\nu &= \left\{ \left\langle (x_i, y_j), \nu_R(x_i, y_j) \right\rangle \mid \nu_R(x_i, y_j) \in S \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

with $T_R(x_i, y_j)$, $I_R(x_i, y_j)$, $F_R(x_i, y_j)$, $\mu_R(x_i, y_j)$, $\eta_R(x_i, y_j)$, and $\nu_R(x_i, y_j)$ are truth, indeterminacy, and falsity of primary and secondary memberships in S respectively.

Next, based on Definition 8, Definition 9 is obtained for the conditions for sets of points in two universes.

Definition 9 (Conditions of T2NPR)

Let \hat{P} and \hat{Q} are two sets of T2NP written as follows:

$$\hat{P} = \left\{ \left\langle x_i, T_P(x_i), I_P(x_i), F_P(x_i), \mu_P(x_i), \eta_P(x_i), \nu_P(x_i) \right\rangle \mid x_i \in X, T_P(x_i), I_P(x_i), F_P(x_i), \mu_P(x_i), \eta_P(x_i), \nu_P(x_i) \in S \right\}$$

$$\hat{Q} = \left\{ \left\langle y_j, T_Q(y_j), I_Q(y_j), F_Q(y_j), \mu_Q(y_j), \eta_Q(y_j), \nu_Q(y_j) \right\rangle \mid y_j \in Y, T_Q(y_j), I_Q(y_j), F_Q(y_j), \mu_Q(y_j), \eta_Q(y_j), \nu_Q(y_j) \in S \right\}$$

Thus, \hat{R} is T2NPR on \hat{P} and \hat{Q} if

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_R(x_i, y_j) &\leq T_P(x_i) \text{ and } T_Q(y_j) \in S, \forall (x_i, y_j) \in X \times Y \\
 I_R(x_i, y_j) &\geq I_P(x_i) \text{ and } I_Q(y_j) \in S, \forall (x_i, y_j) \in X \times Y \\
 F_R(x_i, y_j) &\geq F_P(x_i) \text{ and } F_Q(y_j) \in S, \forall (x_i, y_j) \in X \times Y \\
 \mu_R(x_i, y_j) &\leq \mu_P(x_i) \text{ and } \mu_Q(y_j) \in S, \forall (x_i, y_j) \in X \times Y \\
 \eta_R(x_i, y_j) &\geq \eta_P(x_i) \text{ and } \eta_Q(y_j) \in S, \forall (x_i, y_j) \in X \times Y \\
 \nu_R(x_i, y_j) &\geq \nu(x_i) \text{ and } \nu_Q(y_j) \in S, \forall (x_i, y_j) \in X \times Y
 \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_R(x_i, y_j) &\leq T_{P \times Q}(x_i, y_j) \quad I_R(x_i, y_j) \geq I_{P \times Q}(x_i, y_j) \quad F_R(x_i, y_j) \geq F_{P \times Q}(x_i, y_j) \\
 \mu_R(x_i, y_j) &\leq \mu_{P \times Q}(x_i, y_j) \quad \eta_R(x_i, y_j) \geq \eta_{P \times Q}(x_i, y_j) \quad \nu_R(x_i, y_j) \leq \nu_{P \times Q}(x_i, y_j)
 \end{aligned}$$

with Equation (9) is obeyed.

Then, Definition 8, can be expanded in the universe $X \times Y \times Z$ and written as Definition 10.

Definition 10 (T2NPR for $X \times Y \times Z$ universes)

Let $X \times Y \times Z$ is the collection of point sets, thus \hat{R} is T2NPR defined as

$$\hat{R} = \left\{ \left\langle \left((x_i, y_j, z_k), T_R(x_i, y_j, z_k), I_R(x_i, y_j, z_k), F_R(x_i, y_j, z_k), \right. \right. \right. \quad (11)$$

$$\left. \left. \left. \mu_R(x_i, y_j, z_k), \eta_R(x_i, y_j, z_k), \nu_R(x_i, y_j, z_k) \right) \right. \right.$$

$$\left. \left. \left. \left. \left. \left. \left. T_R(x_i, y_j, z_k), I_R(x_i, y_j, z_k), F_R(x_i, y_j, z_k), \right. \right. \right. \right. \right.$$

$$\left. \left. \left. \left. \left. \left. \left. \mu_R(x_i, y_j, z_k), \eta_R(x_i, y_j, z_k), \nu_R(x_i, y_j, z_k) \in S \right. \right. \right. \right. \right.$$

where $S \in [0,1]$, $T_R(x_i, y_j, z_k): X \times Y \times Z \rightarrow S$, $I_R(x_i, y_j, z_k): X \times Y \times Z \rightarrow S$, $F_R(x_i, y_j, z_k): X \times Y \times Z \rightarrow S$, $\mu_R(x_i, y_j, z_k): X \times Y \times Z \rightarrow S$, $\eta_R(x_i, y_j, z_k): X \times Y \times Z \rightarrow S$ and $\nu_R(x_i, y_j, z_k): X \times Y \times Z \rightarrow S$ that obey the condition

$$0 \leq T_R(x_i, y_j, z_k) + I_R(x_i, y_j, z_k) + F_R(x_i, y_j, z_k) \leq 3 \quad (12)$$

where $T_R(x_i, y_i), I_R(x_i, y_i), F_R(x_i, y_i), \mu_R(x_i, y_i), \eta_R(x_i, y_i), \nu_R(x_i, y_i) \rightarrow [0,1]$ for all $(x_i, y_i) \in X \times Y$.

From Equations (4.4), \hat{R} are represented as T2NPR that consists of neutrosophic relation point denoted as $R^T, R^I, R^F, R^\mu, R^\eta$ and R^ν for truth, indeterminacy, and falsity for primary and secondary memberships, respectively. If Equations (4.5) is fulfilled, there exists $R^T, R^I, R^F, R^\mu, R^\eta$ and R^ν that is stated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 R^T &= \left\{ \left\langle (x_i, y_j, z_k), T_R(x_i, y_j, z_k) \right\rangle \mid T_R(x_i, y_j, z_k) \in S \right\}; \\
 R^\mu &= \left\{ \left\langle (x_i, y_j, z_k), \mu_R(x_i, y_j, z_k) \right\rangle \mid \mu_R(x_i, y_j, z_k) \in S \right\}; \\
 R^I &= \left\{ \left\langle (x_i, y_j, z_k), I_R(x_i, y_j, z_k) \right\rangle \mid I_R(x_i, y_j, z_k) \in S \right\}; \\
 R^\eta &= \left\{ \left\langle (x_i, y_j, z_k), \eta_R(x_i, y_j, z_k) \right\rangle \mid \eta_R(x_i, y_j, z_k) \in S \right\}; \\
 R^F &= \left\{ \left\langle (x_i, y_j, z_k), F_R(x_i, y_j, z_k) \right\rangle \mid F_R(x_i, y_j, z_k) \in S \right\}; \\
 R^\nu &= \left\{ \left\langle (x_i, y_j, z_k), \nu_R(x_i, y_j, z_k) \right\rangle \mid \nu_R(x_i, y_j, z_k) \in S \right\}
 \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

with $T_R(x_i, y_j, z_k), I_R(x_i, y_j, z_k), F_R(x_i, y_j, z_k), \mu_R(x_i, y_j, z_k), \eta_R(x_i, y_j, z_k),$ and $\nu_R(x_i, y_j, z_k)$ are truth, indeterminacy, and falsity of primary and secondary memberships in S respectively.

Next, based on Definition 10, Definition 11 is obtained for the conditions for sets of points in three universes.

Definition 11 (Conditions of T2NPR for $X \times Y \times Z$ universes)

Let \hat{P}, \hat{Q} and \hat{U} are three sets of T2NP written as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{P} &= \left\{ \left\langle x_i, T_P(x_i), I_P(x_i), F_P(x_i), \mu_P(x_i), \eta_P(x_i), \nu_P(x_i) \right\rangle \mid \right. \\ &\quad \left. x_i \in X, T_P(x_i), I_P(x_i), F_P(x_i), \mu_P(x_i), \eta_P(x_i), \nu_P(x_i) \in S \right\} \\ \hat{Q} &= \left\{ \left\langle y_j, T_Q(y_j), I_Q(y_j), F_Q(y_j), \mu_Q(y_j), \eta_Q(y_j), \nu_Q(y_j) \right\rangle \mid \right. \\ &\quad \left. y_j \in Y, T_Q(y_j), I_Q(y_j), F_Q(y_j), \mu_Q(y_j), \eta_Q(y_j), \nu_Q(y_j) \in S \right\} \\ \hat{U} &= \left\{ \left\langle z_k, T_U(z_k), I_U(z_k), F_U(z_k), \mu_U(z_k), \eta_U(z_k), \nu_U(z_k) \right\rangle \mid \right. \\ &\quad \left. z_k \in Z, T_U(z_k), I_U(z_k), F_U(z_k), \mu_U(z_k), \eta_U(z_k), \nu_U(z_k) \in S \right\} \end{aligned}$$

Thus, \hat{R} is T2NPR on \hat{P}, \hat{Q} and \hat{U} if

$$\begin{aligned} T_R(x_i, y_j, z_k) &\leq T_P(x_i), T_Q(y_j), T_U(z_k) \in S, \forall (x_i, y_j, z_k) \in X \times Y \times Z \\ I_R(x_i, y_j, z_k) &\geq I_P(x_i), I_Q(y_j), I_U(z_k) \in S, \forall (x_i, y_j, z_k) \in X \times Y \times Z \\ F_R(x_i, y_j, z_k) &\geq F_P(x_i), F_Q(y_j), F_U(z_k) \in S, \forall (x_i, y_j, z_k) \in X \times Y \times Z \\ \mu_R(x_i, y_j, z_k) &\leq \mu_P(x_i), \mu_Q(y_j), \mu_U(z_k) \in S, \forall (x_i, y_j, z_k) \in X \times Y \times Z \\ \eta_R(x_i, y_j, z_k) &\geq \eta_P(x_i), \eta_Q(y_j), \eta_U(z_k) \in S, \forall (x_i, y_j, z_k) \in X \times Y \times Z \\ \nu_R(x_i, y_j, z_k) &\geq \nu_P(x_i), \nu_Q(y_j), \nu_U(z_k) \in S, \forall (x_i, y_j, z_k) \in X \times Y \times Z \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} T_R(x_i, y_j, z_k) &\leq T_{P \times Q}(x_i, y_j, z_k) & I_R(x_i, y_j, z_k) &\geq I_{P \times Q}(x_i, y_j, z_k) & F_R(x_i, y_j, z_k) &\geq F_{P \times Q}(x_i, y_j, z_k) \\ \mu_R(x_i, y_j, z_k) &\leq \mu_{P \times Q}(x_i, y_j, z_k) & \eta_R(x_i, y_j, z_k) &\geq \eta_{P \times Q}(x_i, y_j, z_k) & \nu_R(x_i, y_j, z_k) &\leq \nu_{P \times Q}(x_i, y_j, z_k) \end{aligned}$$

with Equation (12) is obeyed.

Therefore, based on Definitions 8 and 10, and in the context of neutrosophic geometric modeling, T2NCPR is defined as in Definition 12. In this study, T2NPR and T2NCPR refer to the same point.

Definition 12 (Type-2 neutrosophic control point relation)

Suppose \hat{P} is T2NCPR, then $\hat{P}^T, \hat{P}^I, \hat{P}^F, \hat{P}_i^\mu, \hat{P}_i^\eta$ and \hat{P}_i^ν denoted as T2NCPRs for truth, indeterminacy, and falsity of primary and secondary memberships respectively, where $i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n$, and the position vector of n as control polygon vertices.

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{P}_i^T &= \{ \hat{p}_0^T, \hat{p}_1^T, \hat{p}_2^T, \dots, \hat{p}_n^T \}; & \hat{P}_i^\mu &= \{ \hat{p}_0^\mu, \hat{p}_1^\mu, \hat{p}_2^\mu, \dots, \hat{p}_n^\mu \}; \\ \hat{P}_i^I &= \{ \hat{p}_0^I, \hat{p}_1^I, \hat{p}_2^I, \dots, \hat{p}_n^I \}; & \hat{P}_i^\eta &= \{ \hat{p}_0^\eta, \hat{p}_1^\eta, \hat{p}_2^\eta, \dots, \hat{p}_n^\eta \}; \\ \hat{P}_i^F &= \{ \hat{p}_0^F, \hat{p}_1^F, \hat{p}_2^F, \dots, \hat{p}_n^F \}; & \hat{P}_i^\nu &= \{ \hat{p}_0^\nu, \hat{p}_1^\nu, \hat{p}_2^\nu, \dots, \hat{p}_n^\nu \} \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

Example 4.1

Suppose $\hat{X} = \{2, 4, 6, 8\}$ and $\hat{Y} = \{1, 3, 5, 7\}$ are T2NS over the two universal sets, $X \times Y$. Thus, $\hat{P}_{i,j}^T$, $\hat{P}_{i,j}^I$, $\hat{P}_{i,j}^F$, $\hat{P}_{i,j}^\mu$, $\hat{P}_{i,j}^\eta$ and $\hat{P}_{i,j}^\nu$ denoted as T2NCNR for truth, indeterminacy, and falsity membership for primary and secondary grades where $i = 0, 1, 2, 3$ and $j = 0, 1, 2, 3$.

$$\hat{R}_{i,j} = \left\{ \begin{aligned} &\langle (2,1), 0.6, 0.2, 0.5, 0.9, 0.3, 0.4 \rangle, \langle (4,1), 0.3, 0.3, 0.8, 0.6, 0.5, 0.7 \rangle, \\ &\langle (6,1), 0.8, 0.5, 0.4, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3 \rangle, \langle (8,1), 0.8, 0.1, 0.4, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6 \rangle, \\ &\langle (2,3), 0.5, 0.1, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9 \rangle, \langle (4,3), 1.0, 0.4, 0.1, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3 \rangle, \\ &\langle (6,3), 0.9, 0.7, 0.3, 0.4, 0.3, 0.2 \rangle, \langle (8,3), 0.8, 0.1, 0.4, 0.8, 0.9, 0.1 \rangle, \\ &\langle (2,5), 0.4, 0.2, 0.7, 0.5, 0.2, 0.5 \rangle, \langle (4,5), 0.7, 0.3, 0.3, 0.7, 0.5, 0.3 \rangle, \\ &\langle (6,5), 1.0, 0.1, 0.1, 0.5, 0.3, 0.1 \rangle, \langle (8,5), 0.8, 0.6, 0.4, 0.6, 0.5, 0.3 \rangle, \\ &\langle (2,7), 0.8, 0.3, 0.8, 0.3, 0.5, 0.1 \rangle, \langle (4,7), 0.2, 0.2, 0.3, 0.6, 0.2, 0.5 \rangle, \\ &\langle (6,7), 0.4, 0.9, 0.2, 0.9, 0.3, 0.5 \rangle, \langle (8,7), 0.7, 0.1, 0.4, 0.1, 0.2, 0.5 \rangle \end{aligned} \right\}$$

$$\hat{P}_{i,j}^T = \begin{Bmatrix} 0.6 & 0.3 & 0.8 & 0.8 \\ 0.5 & 1.0 & 0.9 & 0.8 \\ 0.4 & 0.7 & 0.1 & 0.8 \\ 0.8 & 0.2 & 0.4 & 0.7 \end{Bmatrix}, \hat{P}_{i,j}^I = \begin{Bmatrix} 0.2 & 0.3 & 0.5 & 0.1 \\ 0.1 & 0.4 & 0.7 & 0.1 \\ 0.2 & 0.3 & 0.1 & 0.6 \\ 0.3 & 0.2 & 0.9 & 0.1 \end{Bmatrix}, \hat{P}_{i,j}^F = \begin{Bmatrix} 0.5 & 0.8 & 0.4 & 0.4 \\ 0.6 & 0.1 & 0.3 & 0.4 \\ 0.7 & 0.3 & 0.1 & 0.4 \\ 0.8 & 0.3 & 0.2 & 0.4 \end{Bmatrix}$$

$$\hat{P}_{i,j}^\mu = \begin{Bmatrix} 0.9 & 0.6 & 0.1 & 0.4 \\ 0.7 & 0.1 & 0.4 & 0.8 \\ 0.5 & 0.7 & 0.5 & 0.6 \\ 0.3 & 0.6 & 0.9 & 0.1 \end{Bmatrix}, \hat{P}_{i,j}^\eta = \begin{Bmatrix} 0.3 & 0.5 & 0.2 & 0.5 \\ 0.8 & 0.2 & 0.3 & 0.9 \\ 0.2 & 0.5 & 0.3 & 0.5 \\ 0.5 & 0.2 & 0.3 & 0.2 \end{Bmatrix}, \hat{P}_{i,j}^\nu = \begin{Bmatrix} 0.4 & 0.7 & 0.3 & 0.6 \\ 0.9 & 0.3 & 0.2 & 0.1 \\ 0.5 & 0.3 & 0.1 & 0.3 \\ 0.1 & 0.5 & 0.5 & 0.5 \end{Bmatrix}$$

or in a table form T2NCNR with its respective degrees $\langle \hat{P}_{i,j}^T, \hat{P}_{i,j}^I, \hat{P}_{i,j}^F, \hat{P}_{i,j}^\mu, \hat{P}_{i,j}^\eta, \hat{P}_{i,j}^\nu \rangle$ can be written as

Table 1 Type-2 neutrosophic control points with their respective degrees $\langle \hat{P}_{i,j}^T, \hat{P}_{i,j}^I, \hat{P}_{i,j}^F, \hat{P}_{i,j}^\mu, \hat{P}_{i,j}^\eta, \hat{P}_{i,j}^\nu \rangle$

	$\langle \hat{P}_{i,j}^T, \hat{P}_{i,j}^I, \hat{P}_{i,j}^F, \hat{P}_{i,j}^\mu, \hat{P}_{i,j}^\eta, \hat{P}_{i,j}^\nu \rangle$			
	$y_0 = 1$	$y_1 = 3$	$y_2 = 5$	$y_3 = 7$
$x_0 = 2$	$\langle 0.6, 0.2, 0.5, \rangle$ $\langle 0.9, 0.3, 0.4 \rangle$	$\langle 0.5, 0.1, 0.6, \rangle$ $\langle 0.7, 0.8, 0.9 \rangle$	$\langle 0.4, 0.2, 0.7, \rangle$ $\langle 0.5, 0.2, 0.5 \rangle$	$\langle 0.8, 0.3, 0.8, \rangle$ $\langle 0.3, 0.5, 0.1 \rangle$
$x_1 = 4$	$\langle 0.3, 0.3, 0.8, \rangle$ $\langle 0.6, 0.5, 0.7 \rangle$	$\langle 1.0, 0.4, 0.1, \rangle$ $\langle 0.1, 0.2, 0.3 \rangle$	$\langle 0.7, 0.3, 0.3, \rangle$ $\langle 0.7, 0.5, 0.3 \rangle$	$\langle 0.2, 0.2, 0.3, \rangle$ $\langle 0.6, 0.2, 0.5 \rangle$
$x_2 = 6$	$\langle 0.8, 0.5, 0.4, \rangle$ $\langle 0.1, 0.2, 0.3 \rangle$	$\langle 0.9, 0.7, 0.3, \rangle$ $\langle 0.4, 0.3, 0.2 \rangle$	$\langle 1.0, 0.1, 0.1, \rangle$ $\langle 0.5, 0.3, 0.1 \rangle$	$\langle 0.4, 0.9, 0.2, \rangle$ $\langle 0.9, 0.3, 0.5 \rangle$
$x_3 = 8$	$\langle 0.8, 0.1, 0.4, \rangle$ $\langle 0.4, 0.5, 0.6 \rangle$	$\langle 0.8, 0.1, 0.4, \rangle$ $\langle 0.8, 0.9, 0.1 \rangle$	$\langle 0.8, 0.6, 0.4, \rangle$ $\langle 0.6, 0.5, 0.3 \rangle$	$\langle 0.7, 0.1, 0.4, \rangle$ $\langle 0.1, 0.2, 0.5 \rangle$

Then, the T2NNR and T2NCNR are illustrated in Figure 1. Based on the value of $\langle \hat{P}_{i,j}^T, \hat{P}_{i,j}^I, \hat{P}_{i,j}^F, \hat{P}_{i,j}^\mu, \hat{P}_{i,j}^\eta, \hat{P}_{i,j}^\nu \rangle$, there exist degrees of truth, indeterminacy, and falsity of primary and secondary memberships that satisfy Equation (12) based on the example in Table 1.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

Figure 1 The T2NCNR over the universal set $X \times Y$ for primary (a) Truth; (b) Indeterminacy; (c) Falsity memberships. And secondary, (d) Truth; (e) Indeterminacy; (f) Falsity memberships

4. Properties and Structures of Type-2 Neutrosophic Control Point Relation (T2NCPR)

T2NS consists of a union of T2NCPs. In this section, properties and structures for T2NCPR are discussed. Therefore, Propositions 1 to 2 demonstrated the relations and structures of T2NSs and T2NPs based on Section 2 as follows:

Proposition 1: Every T2NS is the Union of Its T2NPs

Let \hat{A} be a T2NS over X . Then,

$$\hat{A} = \bigcup \left\{ P = \langle x, (T, \mu), (I, \eta), (F, \nu) \rangle : P \in \hat{A} \right\} \tag{12}$$

Proof:

1. At each point $x \in X$, the T2NS assigns:
 - $\hat{A}_T(x)$ is a NS over $[0,1]$, which contains pairs (T, μ) ,
 - Similarly, $\hat{A}_I(x)$ and $\hat{A}_F(x)$ contain (I, η) and (F, ν) .
2. From T2FS, we know that $\hat{A}_T(x) = \bigcup \left\{ (T, \mu) : (T, \mu) \in \hat{A}_T(x) \right\}$.
3. Therefore, for each x , we can define T2NPs as $P_x^{T, \mu, I, \eta, F, \nu} = \langle x, (T, \mu), (I, \eta), (F, \nu) \rangle$ for all values in the NSs.
4. Taking the union of all such points gives $\hat{A}(x) = \bigcup \left\{ P_x \in \hat{A} \right\}$.
5. Extending to all $x \in X$, we get $\hat{A} = \bigcup \left\{ P : P \in \hat{A} \right\}$. ■

Proposition 2: Equality of T2NS via T2NPs

Two T2NSs \hat{A} and \hat{B} are equal if and only if every T2NP that belongs to \hat{A} also belongs to \hat{B} , and vice versa. That is:

$$\hat{A} = \hat{B} \Leftrightarrow \forall P, P \in \hat{A} \Leftrightarrow P \in \hat{B} \tag{13}$$

Proof:

(\Rightarrow Direction):

1. If $\hat{A} = \hat{B}$, then their NSs at each $x \in X$ are equal: $\hat{A}_T(x) = \hat{B}_T(x)$, $\hat{A}_I(x) = \hat{B}_I(x)$, $\hat{A}_F(x) = \hat{B}_F(x)$
2. Thus, for any pair $(T, \mu) \in \hat{A}_T(x)$ must also be in $\hat{B}_T(x)$, and likewise for indeterminacy and falsity.
3. Therefore, every T2NP that belongs to \hat{A} must belong to \hat{B} , and vice versa.

(\Leftarrow Direction):

1. Suppose every T2NP in \hat{A} must belong to \hat{B} , and vice versa.
2. Then, at each x , all neutrosophic grade (T, μ) , (I, η) and (F, ν) from $\hat{A}(x)$ are in $\hat{B}(x)$, and vice versa.
3. Therefore, $\hat{A}_T(x) = \hat{B}_T(x)$, $\hat{A}_I(x) = \hat{B}_I(x)$, $\hat{A}_F(x) = \hat{B}_F(x)$.

4. So, $\hat{A} = \hat{B}$. ■

Proposition 3: Inclusion Implies Membership Transfer

If $\hat{A} \subseteq \hat{B}$ and $P \in \hat{A}$, then $P \in \hat{B}$.

Proof:

1. Let $P = \langle x, (T, \mu), (I, \eta), (F, \nu) \rangle \in \hat{A}$.
2. By definition of $P \in \hat{A}$, we have $(T, \mu) \in \hat{A}_T(x)$, $(I, \eta) \in \hat{A}_I(x)$ and $(F, \nu) \in \hat{A}_F(x)$.
3. If $\hat{A} \subseteq \hat{B}$, then $\hat{A}_T(x) \subseteq \hat{B}_T(x)$, $\hat{A}_I(x) \subseteq \hat{B}_I(x)$ and $\hat{A}_F(x) \subseteq \hat{B}_F(x)$.
4. Therefore, $(T, \mu) \in \hat{B}_T(x)$, $(I, \eta) \in \hat{B}_I(x)$, and $(F, \nu) \in \hat{B}_F(x)$.
5. Hence, $P \in \hat{B}$. ■

Proposition 4: T2NP in Intersection of Sets

$P \in \bigcap_{i \in M} \hat{A}_i \Leftrightarrow P \in \hat{A}_i$ for all i .

Proof:

(\Rightarrow Direction):

1. If $P \in \bigcap \hat{A}_i$, then $(T, \mu) \in \bigcap \hat{A}_i^T(x)$, so $(T, \mu) \in \hat{A}_i^T(x) \forall i$.
2. Same for (I, η) and (F, ν) . Hence, $P \in \hat{A}_i$ for all i .

(\Leftarrow Direction):

1. If $P \in \hat{A}_i$ for all i , then each component $(T, \mu), (I, \eta)$ and (F, ν) belongs to each neutrosophic set involved.
2. Thus, it belongs to the intersection set. ■

Proposition 5: T2NP in a Union of Sets

If $P \in \hat{A}_j$ for some j , then $P \in \bigcup_i \hat{A}_i$.

Proof:

1. Since the union is defined as $\hat{A}^T(x) = \bigcup_i \hat{A}_i^T(x)$.
2. If $(T, \mu) \in \hat{A}_j^T(x)$, then $(T, \mu) \in \hat{A}_j^T \cup \hat{A}_j^T(x)$.
3. Similarly, for the indeterminacy and falsity components.
4. Hence, $P \in \bigcup \hat{A}_i$. ■

Proposition 6: Existence of a Component Containing a T2NP

If $P \in \bigcup \hat{A}_i$, then $\exists \hat{A}_j$ such that $P \in \hat{A}_j$.

Proof:

1. The definition of a union guarantees that any element in it must come from **at least one** of the sets.
2. So, if $(T, \mu) \in \bigcup \hat{A}_i^T(x)$, it must be in some $\hat{A}_i^T(x)$, and similarly for the other components.
3. Hence, the whole point P is in some \hat{A}_j . ■

5. Conclusions

By introducing T2NCP, this research has introduced the T2NCPR model. T2NCPR is a perfect method for modeling data with neutrosophic properties because it has membership, non-membership, and indeterminacy functions. All the data will be processed and examined using these features. Economics, real-time tracking, stock market, data mining, databases, wireless sensor networks, management decision-making, random processes, routing, and remote sensing are among the fields in which T2NCPR can be used. The ability to visualize neutrosophic data using any type of geometric modeling curve or surface is crucial for understanding and characterizing the nature of certain issues and circumstances and providing logical explanations for them. Both the process and the finished model will be able to advance the study of fuzzy modeling methods.

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